

Detecting Natural Hydrogen at the Surface: Remote Sensing of Sub-Circular Depressions (SCDs)

What are Circular or Sub-Circular Depressions (SCDs)?

Across Africa and other parts of the world, researchers have discovered a link between natural hydrogen escaping from underground and the formation of shallow, round-shaped depressions at the Earth's surface (see Figure 1). These features, often lacking vegetation, are sometimes called "**fairy circles**" or "**pans**", and they can serve as visual clues for finding underground hydrogen sources.

Figure 1 Satellite image of sub-Circular depressions.

What Makes These Depressions Special?

While other natural processes like sinkholes or glacial activity can also form depressions, hydrogen-related SCDs usually show a **clear reduction in vegetation**. This unique fingerprint helps scientists tell them apart.

How Can We Detect Them?

Using satellite and aerial imagery, the SCDs can be mapped remotely, from a computer, before field visits are conducted. This makes hydrogen exploration faster, safer, and more efficient.

Main Remote Sensing Tools Used in HyAfrica:

Satellite Images: Platforms like Landsat 7/8/9 and Sentinel-2 provide free, high-resolution images covering large areas.

Google Earth: Offers easy-to-use images

Figure 3 Google Earth image of SCDs in arid terrain.

for visual identification, often in very high spatial resolution, though it lacks detailed spectral data ready for use (see Figure 2).

Digital Elevation Models (DEM): These help map subtle terrain variations that reveal depressions.

Spectral Indices: The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) highlights vegetation health. Since SCDs often have little or no vegetation, NDVI helps locate them by detecting "bare" spots (see figure 3).

Figure 2 NDVI image.

Why does NDVI Work?

NDVI compares light in the red and near-infrared ranges. Healthy plants reflect NIR but absorb red, while bare soil or degraded areas show much lower values. In dry or semi-arid regions, NDVI maps can clearly outline SCDs (see Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4 SDCs Detection (in red).

Figure 5 Large area screening (SDCs represented as yellow).

Other Indices Used:

Depending on the environment, other spectral indices like the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) or Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI) might better detect water or soil variations inside SCDs. Multiple indexes and reflectance bands from the imagery can also be combined to better detect SCDs particularities.

Alternative methods and tools:

LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging):

LiDAR uses laser pulses from drones or planes to create ultra-detailed 3D maps of the land surface. It can detect small, shallow depressions under vegetation or in flat terrain that other methods might miss. This is especially useful in forested or hilly areas.

Thermal Imaging: Temperature-sensitive cameras (from drones or satellites) can reveal subtle changes in ground heat, which may be influenced by hydrogen emissions.

Digital Terrain Analysis (DTA): By analyzing patterns in slope, curvature, and drainage, researchers can identify natural depressions that could be linked to hydrogen seeps.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): Machine learning classification algorithms can be used to enhance the identification and extraction of SDCs objects from satellite/aerial imagery by using Object Based Image Analysis (OBIA) instead of evaluating imagery pixels individually. This approach has the advantage of considering characteristics of neighbor pixels, or regions of pixels, in the identification and extraction of features representing SDCs,

Conclusion

Detecting potential hydrogen seeping SDCs at the Earth's surface is easier due to satellite data, vegetation indices and machine learning. Mapping of SDCs for large areas provides a fundamental, fast and cost-effective way of assessment that allows a better planning of in-situ soil gas testing.